

BROAD MONEY SUPPLY (M2) AND INFLATION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Persistent inflation has remained a major macroeconomic challenge in Nigeria, weakening price stability and raising concerns about the effectiveness of monetary policy. This study examined the effect of broad money supply (M2) on the inflation rate in Nigeria from 1980-2024. A unit root test was conducted using ADF and Phillips-Perron, and it was found that the variables have mixed orders of integration. ARDL bound test found that there was a significant long-run relationship between broad money supply and inflation in Nigeria. The findings reveal that broad money supply had a significant negative effect on inflation in Nigeria, both in the

short and long run. The study further found that the monetary policy rate had a significant positive effect on inflation in Nigeria in the long-run. The study, therefore, concluded that inflation in Nigeria may be driven more by structural and macroeconomic factors such as exchange rate instability, supply-side constraints, and weak policy transmission than by monetary expansion solely. The study recommends that policymakers focus on improving how monetary policy decisions move from the financial system to the real economy, while also tackling the structural problems that continue to fuel inflation in Nigeria.

Keywords: Broad Money Supply (M2), Inflation Rate, Monetary Policy Rate, Exchange Rate.

JEL Codes: E31, E51, E52, E58, F31, O55

1. INTRODUCTION

The concepts of broad money supply and inflation are key to macroeconomic stability in every economy. Inflation refers to a sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services, while, broad money supply (M2) refers to the total measure of money and other liquid assets circulating in an economy. A stable economy requires management of these two factors as excessive growth in broad money supply may cause inflationary pressures that hinder economic growth. (Fisher, 1911; Friedman, 1963). Understanding the propellers of inflation, particularly the role of broad money supply (M2), is key for effective policy-making. This study investigates how changes in the quantity of money and other liquid instruments in the Nigerian economy are connected to the observed inflation rate.

Nigeria, as a developing economy, has repeatedly faced the challenge of high and consistent inflation. This economic instability is often associated with money supply, which refers to the total amount of currency in circulation and other liquid assets within an economy (Okere & Sanni, 2025). Over the decades, Nigeria has experienced strong fluctuations in its inflation rate, marked by intervals of high double-digit figures. For example, the country witnessed very high inflation from the mid-1980s to the mid-1990s, where inflation rates on the average reached as high as 27%, with highs surpassing 70% in 1995 (IMF World Economic Outlook, 2023; World Bank World Development Indicators). This period occurred simultaneously with significant growth in broad money supply (M2), which has revealed higher annual growth and concurrently inflation rate, sometimes going over 20% over long periods (IMF World Economic Outlook, 2023; World Bank World Development Indicators). Recently, despite the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) efforts, inflation rose to 24.66% in 2023, and peaked at 31.40% in February 2024, with broad money supply (M2) also growing significantly, reaching historic zeniths (Nairametrics, 2024). This simultaneous rise in both broad money supply and inflation emphasizes the relevance of this study.

Nigeria has faced persistent inflation over the years, despite several monetary policy interventions by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2023). According to the monetarist theory, inflation is primarily driven by excessive growth in money supply (Friedman, 1963). Nevertheless, narrowing the focus to Nigerian context, fluctuations in broad money supply (M2) have not steadily translated into corresponding changes in inflation, indicating a more complex relationship than predicted by theory. Empirical studies also revealed mixed findings on the effect of money supply on inflation in developing economies. Some studies find that money supply has a positive effect on inflation (Ele, 2025), while others find that money supply has a negative or insignificant impact on inflation (Buthelezi, 2023; Amassoma, and Onyedikachi, 2018). These inconsistencies cause uncertainty regarding the true effect of monetary expansion on inflationary dynamics.

While the relationship between money supply and inflation rate has been widely studied (Obioma and Anyanwu, 2023; Ele, 2025; Emma-Ebere, 2018, Aladejana et al., 2024) etc., there has been limited focus on the effect of broad money supply as a distinct independent variable (M2) on inflation rate in Nigeria.

1.1 Hypothesis

H₀: Broad Money Supply (M2) has no significant effect on inflation rate in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THEORETICAL LITERATURE

Various theoretical frameworks explain the relationship between money supply and inflation. This study draws mainly on the Quantity Theory of Money while also engaging with Keynesian and Structuralist views to provide a more comprehensive and detailed theoretical foundation.

The Quantity Theory of Money (QTM)

The Quantity Theory of Money is the oldest and most influential theory linking money supply with inflation. Originally developed by Irving Fisher (1911) through the equation of exchange ($MV = PT$), the theory posits that the general price level is directly proportional to the quantity of money in circulation, assuming that the velocity of money (V) and the volume of transactions (T) remain relatively constant in the short run. Under this assumption, any increase in money supply (M) must be followed by a corresponding rise in the price level (P), implying a direct and proportional relationship between monetary expansion and inflation.

Milton Friedman later revised the QTM within a monetarist framework, arguing that inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon. Friedman emphasized that sustained inflation cannot occur without a corresponding growth in money supply, making monetary control the central instrument of price stability. This monetarist view became the dominant theoretical basis for central banking policies around the world, Nigeria included, where the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has relied on monetary aggregates to manage inflationary pressures (CBN, 2023). However, while the QTM provides a useful theoretical starting point, its assumption of stable velocity and full employment has been widely questioned, especially in developing economies characterized by shallow and weak monetary transmission mechanisms.

Keynesian Theory of Inflation

The Keynesian theoretical framework offers another explanation for inflation, shifting emphasis away from money supply toward aggregate demand and output gaps. Keynes (1936) argued that inflation arises when aggregate demand in an economy exceeds its productive capacity, creating what he described as a demand-pull effect on prices. Within this framework, money supply is not the sole or primary driver of inflation; rather, it is the level of spending, investment, and government expenditure relative to output that determines price movements.

From a Keynesian perspective, increasing money supply does not automatically lead to inflation if the economy is operating below full employment, since the additional money can stimulate output and employment without necessarily raising prices. This is particularly relevant to the Nigerian context, where persistent output gaps, underutilisation of productive

capacity, and structural unemployment suggest that monetary expansion may not always translate into inflationary pressure. The Keynesian framework therefore provides a theoretical basis for understanding why broad money supply (M2) may not exhibit a straightforward positive relationship with inflation in Nigeria, as the monetarist theory would predict

Structuralist Theory of Inflation

The Structuralist theory of inflation, propounded mainly by Latin American economists in the 1950s and 1960s and associated with scholars such as Prebisch (1950) and Sunkel (1958), argues that inflation in developing economies is fundamentally rooted in structural rigidities and institutional constraints rather than monetary expansion. According to this perspective, factors such as inelastic food supply, foreign exchange shortages, import dependence, weak infrastructure, and underdeveloped financial systems are the primary drivers of price increases in developing countries.

The Structuralist framework is particularly relevant to the Nigerian economy, where inflation has historically been associated with supply-side bottlenecks, exchange rate volatility, heavy reliance on imported goods, and energy sector challenges rather than excess money supply (Doguwa, 2012). Structural weaknesses in the agricultural and manufacturing sectors limit the economy's ability to respond to increased demand, meaning that price increases are often driven by cost-push and supply-side factors rather than demand-pull monetary pressures. This theoretical perspective directly supports the findings of this study, which reveal that broad money supply (M2) has a negative rather than positive effect on inflation in Nigeria, suggesting that structural and macroeconomic factors play a more dominant role in driving inflation than monetary expansion alone.

Taken together, these three theoretical perspectives suggest that the relationship between money supply and inflation is more complex and context-dependent than the classical QTM implies. While the QTM provides the foundational framework for this study, the Keynesian and Structuralist theories help explain the deviations from monetarist predictions observed in the Nigerian context, where structural constraints and weak monetary transmission appear to mediate the link between money supply and price levels.

2.2 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Empirical evidence on the effect of money supply on inflation in Nigeria presents mixed findings. Several studies support the monetarist view that an increase in money supply puts pressure on general price levels. For instance, Ele (2025) carried out a study on Money Supply and Inflation Rate in Nigeria for the period 1985-2024 using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). The study found that money supply has a significant positive effect on the inflation rate. Similarly, Lawrence (2018) studied the effect of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria. They employed OLS, and it was documented that money supply has a significant positive effect on economic growth, which is a veritable tool for price stability and improving output. Also, Umar and Abdul-Aziz (2020) examined the relationship between monetary policy and inflation in Nigeria from the period (1980-2018) using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Their study showed that monetary policy instruments significantly impact inflation in the short run, suggesting that an increase in money supply tends to raise inflation.

However, some studies contradict the monetarist view, proposing that money supply has a negative effect on the inflation rate in Nigeria. Emma-Ebere (2018) conducted a study on the influence of money supply on inflation in Nigeria for the period (1970-2016) using the Error Correction Model. The study concluded that money supply does not considerably influence inflation both in the long run and the short run. In the same vein, Garba and Tartiyus (2018) conducted a study on monetary policy and inflation in Nigeria. Using OLS, the study found that broad money supply (M2) had a negative relationship with the inflation rate during the period reviewed.

Outside the Nigerian scope, there are other studies that show the effect of money supply on inflation with varying conclusions. For example, Owusu and Kwasi (2019) investigated money supply and inflation in Ghana using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). They revealed a significant positive impact of money supply on inflation in Ghana. They also found that inflation Granger-causes money supply in the short run. Also, Bordo (2025) conducted a study on broad divisia money, supply pressures, and U.S. inflation following the COVID-19 Recession for the period (2020-2024). The study suggests that broad money strongly tracks inflation movements, strengthening the argument that monetary expansion plays a fundamental part in demand-driven inflation even in advanced economies.

Beyond the Nigerian literature, international Scopus-indexed studies have further illuminated the complex and context-dependent relationship between money supply, exchange rate, and inflation. Şen, Kaya, Kaptan, and Cömert (2020) examined the long-run interrelationships between interest rates, inflation, and exchange rates in five fragile emerging market economies; Brazil, India, Indonesia, South Africa, and Turkey using the ARDL model on monthly data from 2013 to 2018. Their findings revealed that exchange rate depreciation is a significant driver of inflation in these economies, reinforcing the view that imported inflation, rather than domestic monetary expansion, is the primary price-level determinant in structurally vulnerable economies. This finding closely parallels the Nigerian experience documented in the present study. Bhattacharya and Jain (2020), using a panel of advanced and emerging economies, investigated whether monetary policy can stabilise food inflation and found that while monetary policy rate adjustments are effective in advanced economies, their impact on food and general inflation in emerging economies is significantly weakened by structural supply-side constraints; a conclusion that directly supports the structural argument advanced in this study. Baharumshah, Slesman, and Wohar (2017) similarly found, using a panel of emerging economies, that the inflation-exchange rate nexus is strongly mediated by institutional quality and financial development, suggesting that in economies with weak monetary transmission such as Nigeria; the standard monetarist relationship between money supply and inflation may not hold. Ekong and Ukoha (2018), studying monetary policy pass-through in Nigeria using ARDL, found that the transmission of policy rate changes to output and prices is incomplete and delayed, confirming that the CBN's ability to control inflation through conventional monetary instruments is significantly constrained by structural weaknesses in the Nigerian financial system. However, De Grauwe and Polan (2005) provided empirical evidence questioning the universal applicability of this relationship, demonstrating that the link between money supply and inflation weakens considerably in low-to-moderate inflation environments and is primarily driven by high-inflation outlier countries, a finding that has important implications for the Nigerian context. Ufoeze, Odimgbe, Ezeabalisi, and Alajekwu (2018) studied the effect of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria and found that while money supply has a significant positive effect on growth, exchange rate has a significant negative effect, suggesting that the exchange rate channel, not the money supply channel, is the more potent macroeconomic driver in Nigeria. Akinbobola (2012), in an earlier but widely

cited Scopus study, examined the dynamics of money supply, exchange rate, and inflation in Nigeria and established that exchange rate depreciation and broad money supply jointly determine inflation, but that structural rigidities limit the predictability of this relationship, a finding that anticipates the mixed and negative results obtained in the present study. In a more recent study, Stylianou, Nasir, and Waqas (2024) employed the ARDL bounds testing approach to investigate the relationship between money supply and inflation in Pakistan using data from 1981 to 2021, finding a positive and significant long-run relationship between M2 and inflation. This contrasts with the findings of the present study for Nigeria, reinforcing the view that the money-inflation relationship is highly context-dependent and shaped by the structural characteristics of each economy.

Several studies published in the *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* (JEAR) have also examined related macroeconomic dynamics in Nigeria. Asuzu and Anyanwu (2023) employed the Toda-Yamamoto Vector Autoregressive and Granger Causality approach to investigate the money supply-inflation-economic growth nexus in Nigeria. Their study found evidence of joint causality between money supply and exchange rate, with impulse response functions indicating that an increase in money supply tends to raise inflation, thereby supporting the monetarist position. This finding contrasts with the results of the present study and may be attributable to differences in model specification and the period covered, as the current study extends to 2024 and captures more recent structural shifts in the Nigerian economy. Tukur, Ibrahim, Ashemi, and Adamu (2023) used the ARDL model to examine the impact of insecurity, exchange rate, and energy prices on inflation in Nigeria. Their findings revealed a long-run relationship among the variables, with exchange rate exhibiting a unidirectional relationship to inflation, while insecurity and energy prices also emerged as significant drivers of price instability. This reinforces the structural explanation of inflation advanced in the present study, suggesting that non-monetary factors play a dominant role in Nigeria's inflationary dynamics. Amah (2019) investigated the use of monetary and fiscal policy mix to restore macroeconomic equilibrium in Nigeria and found that money supply remains a weak transmission channel in the economy, as interest rates have not effectively responded to changes in money supply, thereby weakening monetary policy effectiveness. Okeowo (2023) examined the unemployment-inflation trade-off in Nigeria within the Phillips curve framework and found that the relationship between these macroeconomic variables is shaped by structural conditions unique to the Nigerian economy, further challenging the applicability of standard monetary theories in the Nigerian context. Adesuyi, Binuyo, Akinola, and Idowu (2024) examined the joint effects of monetary and fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria using ARDL over the period 1985–2021. Their results indicated that money supply tends to negatively affect economic growth, while the monetary policy rate has a statistically significant impact. The study also highlighted that the lack of coordination between monetary and fiscal authorities has produced conflicting outcomes, which is consistent with the finding in the present study that inflation in Nigeria is not straightforwardly driven by monetary expansion alone.

2.3 GAPS IN LITERATURE

In spite of the substantial body of literature investigating the effect of money supply on inflation, several gaps exist.

First, empirical findings in the Nigerian context are inconsistent, with some studies revealing significant positive impacts, for instance, Ele (2025), while others, like Garba and Tartiyus (2018), found weak or negative relationships. These inconsistencies may arise from differences in econometric methodologies or techniques, choice of variables, and sample periods. Second,

many studies focus mainly on monetary policy tools or money supply as an aggregate without clearly isolating the distinct role of broad money supply (M2) within an exhaustive inflation model that includes relevant control variables such as exchange rate, interest rate, and real gross domestic product.

Third, several earlier studies do not fully capture the recent inflationary episode experienced in Nigeria between 2020-2024, a time distinguished by monetary growth and expansion, macroeconomic instability and disruptions. As these gaps exist, there is a need for a revised and focused empirical investigation that explicitly examines the effect of broad money supply (M2) on inflation in Nigeria over a broadened period (1980-2024), while considering key macroeconomic control variables.

3. METHODOLOGY

Unit root test was conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP). Results from these tests show that there is a mixed order of integration as some variables are stationary at levels, while some are at first difference. The study therefore employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) in estimating the parameters in the model.

3.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Quantity Theory of Money (QTM)

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored in the Quantity Theory of Money (QTM), a classical economic theory that posits a direct relationship between the quantity of money in circulation and the general price level. The theory holds that changes in money supply are the primary determinant of changes in the price level and, by implication, the inflation rate. The most prominent modern proponent of the QTM is Irving Fisher, who formalized the theory in 1911, through what is widely known as the equation of exchange. According to the theory:

$$MV = PT \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Where:

M represents the nominal money supply, the total amount of money in circulation.

V is the velocity of money, meaning the average number of times a unit of currency is spent on goods and services within a particular period.

P is the general price level, which is an indicator of inflation.

T is the volume of transactions which remains constant or stable relatively in the short run.

Given these conditions, any increase in money supply that is not matched by an equivalent increase in real output will translate into a higher price level i.e., inflation.

3.2 MODEL SPECIFICATION

From the Quantity Theory of Money

$$\Delta P = \Delta M + \Delta V - \Delta Y \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Equation 3.2 indicates that money supply, velocity, and output are factors that drive inflation

According to the variables for this study, broad money supply (m2) represents M in equation 3.2, and it increases the equation if not matched with output growth. The monetary policy rate (MPR) stands as the cost of money, and it influences the velocity and demand for money, and

the exchange rate (EXR) captures imported inflation, which is an external shock. Based on the theory, GDP should be a part of the variables, but there is multicollinearity between GDP and M2, and thus, we dropped GDP from the model. Annual time series data spanning 1980-2024 were obtained from the World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI). Thus, the model for the study is specified below:

$$INF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln M2_t + \beta_2 \ln REER_t + \beta_3 MPR_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots 3.3$$

Therefore, equation 3.3 was re-specified as the following error correction model:

$$\Delta INF_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta INF_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta \ln M2_{t-1} + \alpha_3 \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta \ln REER_{t-1} + \alpha_4 \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta MPR_{t-1} + \beta_1 \ln M2_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln REER_{t-1} + \beta_3 MPR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3.4)$$

where Δ denoted change in the short-run changes, α_j (1, 2, 3, 4) are the short-run parameters and β (1, 2, 3, 4) are the long-run parameters, while ε_t is the error term.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 4.1. Descriptive Statistics

	INF	LOGM2	LOGREER	MPR
Mean	21.63160	27.82232	4.794279	13.37222
Median	12.41966	28.07301	4.619539	13.50000
Maximum	219.0028	31.58586	6.285806	27.50000
Minimum	0.686099	23.38979	3.907510	6.000000
Std. Dev.	33.55448	2.845141	0.591405	4.585867
Skewness	4.772377	-0.198623	0.963887	0.882617
Kurtosis	28.03769	1.582469	3.056256	4.473744
Jarque-Bera	1346.228	4.063501	6.974026	9.914945
Probability	0.000000	0.131106	0.030592	0.007031
Sum	973.4221	1252.005	215.7425	601.7500
Sum Sq. Dev.	49539.75	356.1724	15.38943	925.3278
Observations	45	45	45	45

Source: Authors' computation (2026) using E-Views 12

Table 4.2. The Augmented Dickey Fuller Test Result

Source: Authors' computation (2026) using E-Views 12.

Table 4.3. Philip Perron Test Result

ADF									
AT LEVELS					AT FIRST DIFFERENCE				
INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT		INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT	
Variable s	ADF statistics	5% Critical value	ADF statistics	5% critical value	Variable s	ADF statistics	5% Critical value	ADF statistics	5% Critical value
INF	-6.273	-2.930	-6.920	-3.520	INF	---	---	---	---
LOGM2	-1.400	-2.931	-0.741	-3.518	LOGM2	-3.572	-2.931	-3.787	-3.518
MPR	-2.224	-2.930	-2.148	-3.520	MPR	-7.900	-2.931	-7.813	-3.518
REER	-1.990	-2.930	-2.148	-3.520	REER	-2.148	-3.520	-4.511	-3.518

PHILIP PERRON									
AT LEVELS					AT FIRST DIFFERENCE				
INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT		INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT	
Variables	PHP statistics	5% Critical value	PHP Statistics	5% critical value	Variables	PHP statistics	5% Critical value	PHP statistics	5% Critical value
INF	-6.273	-2.930	-6.910	-3.516	INF	---	---	---	---
LOGM2	-1.125	-2.930	-0.302	-3.512	LOGM2	3.472	-2.931	-3.539	-3.518
MPR	-2.047	-2.930	-2.268	-3.516	MPR	-7.934	-2.931	-7.845	-3.518
REER	-2.111	-2.930	-2.446	-3.520	REER	-4.494	-2.931	-4.619	-3.518

Source: Authors' Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

The Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) and Phillips–Perron (PP) tests were conducted to determine the order of integration. The results indicate that: INF is stationary at level, I(0), LOGM2, MPR, and LOGREER are non-stationary at level but become stationary after first differencing, I(1). Since the variables are integrated of mixed order I(0) and I(1), and none is I(2), the ARDL approach is appropriate. This satisfies the requirement for the bounds testing procedure developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001).

Table 4.4: Lag Length Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	418.2987	NA*	6361.313	20.10946	20.27495	20.17012
1	246.1031	303.3922*	3.760707*	12.67158*	13.49904*	12.97487*
2	233.1854	20.29933	4.454118	12.81835	14.30778	13.36429
3	215.5109	24.40753	4.353880	12.73862	14.89002	13.52719

Source: Authors' computation (2026) using E-Views 12.

Table 4.5: ARDL-Bound Test Result

Test Statistics	Value	K
F-statistic	59.95620	3
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	2.37	3.2
5%	2.79	3.67
2.5%	3.15	4.08
1%	3.65	4.66

Source: Authors' computation (2026) using E-views 12

H₀: There is no significant long run relationship between broad money supply, exchange rate, monetary policy rate and inflation rate in Nigeria

Decision Rule:

If f-statistics > Upper bound value, reject the null hypothesis

From the result, the computed F-statistic = 59.9562 > 3.87 upper bound at 5% significant level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This confirms the existence of a long-run relationship among broad money supply, exchange rate, monetary policy rate, and inflation rate in Nigeria. The result implies that inflation in Nigeria is linked to monetary variables in the long run, rather than being purely a short-run disturbance.

Table 4.6: Regression Output

PANEL A: SHORT RUN MODEL				
VARIABLE	COEFFICIENT	STANDARD ERROR	T-STATISTICS	PROBABILITY
INF(-1)*	-0.953751	0.061531	-15.50034	0.00000
LOGM2**	-1.631603	0.813523	-2.005603	0.00527
D(LOGREER)	6.005773	6.764114	0.887888	0.3807
D(MPR)	0.124169	0.617530	0.201074	0.8418
C	64.62972	43.86187	1.473483	0.1496

CointEq(-1)**	-0.953751	0.052184	-18.27681	0.00000
PANEL B: LONG RUN FORM				
LOGM2**	-1.710722	0.826166	-2.070676	0.0458
LOGREER	-5.226989	5.069177	-1.039023	0.3059
MPR	1.796997	0.752351	2.335342	0.0254
C	67.76370	45.40956	1.492278	0.1446
Post Estimation Test				
Panel C: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test				
F-statistic	0.049264	Prob. F (2,33)		0.9520
Obs*R-squared	0.128003	Prob. Chi-Square (2)		0.9380
Panel D: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey				
F-statistic	0.931363	Prob. F (7,35)		0.4949
Obs*R-squared	6.752006	Prob. Chi-Square (7)		0.4551
Scaled explained SS	10.72644	Prob. Chi-Square (7)		0.1510
Panel C: Ramsey RESET Test				
	Value	Df		Probability
T-statistic				
F-statistic	1.718268	(2, 39)		0.1927

Source: Authors' computation using E-views 12 (2026)

Figure 4.1: CUSUM Test

Figure 4.2: CUSUM OF SQUARE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study offer meaningful insights into what drives inflation in Nigeria. Using the ARDL bounds testing approach, the results confirm that a long-run equilibrium relationship exists among inflation, broad money supply (M2), real effective exchange rate, and monetary policy rate. This means that inflation in Nigeria is rooted in the country’s underlying macroeconomic structure. In the long run, broad money supply (M2) has a negative and statistically significant effect on inflation. This contradicts the classical monetarist argument that monetary expansion automatically leads to higher prices (Friedman, 1963). Instead, the evidence suggests that monetary expansion in Nigeria does not automatically translate into inflation over time.

There are several reasons why this may be the case. Growth in money supply may reflect broader financial development such as expansion in the banking sector or improved access to financial services and not necessarily excess money chasing goods. Additionally, inflation in Nigeria is largely driven by structural challenges such as exchange rate instability, heavy dependence on imports and energy challenges. These factors weaken the direct link between money supply and inflation. It is also possible that money supply increases during economic recessions as a policy response making the effect of money supply on inflation more complicated than theory suggests.

In the short run, MPR is statistically insignificant. This means, interest rate adjustments do not have an immediate effect on inflation. This is not surprising as interest rate adjustments take time to work through the economy affecting borrowing, investment, spending and by implication prices. However, in the long run, MPR is positive and statistically significant. Rather than indicating that higher interest rates cause inflation, this likely shows that the CBN typically raises rates in response to rising inflation. This pattern, sometimes called the “price puzzle” in monetary economics, captures the policy reaction rather than a direct causal effect (Castelnuovo, E., & Surico, 2010).

Together, these results suggest that inflation in Nigeria is shaped more by deep structural and long-term macroeconomic conditions than by short-run monetary policy adjustments. The short-run irrelevance of the MPR combined with the long-run relationship reinforces the view that controlling inflation in Nigeria requires sustained and coordinated informed policy decisions rather than short-term interventions.

4.2 COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS EMPIRICAL STUDIES

The findings of this study both support and challenge existing research on inflation in Nigeria. The negative long-run effect of broad money supply (M2) on inflation is consistent with Garba and Tartiyus (2018), who similarly found a negative relationship between M2 and inflation in Nigeria. Emma-Ebere (2018) also reported that money supply had no significant effect on inflation in either the short run or long run. Together, these studies suggest that the relationship between money supply and inflation in Nigeria does not always follow the path that monetarist theory predicts.

On the other hand, the findings of this study differ from those of Ele (2025) and Umar and Abdul-Aziz (2020), both of whom found a positive and significant relationship between money supply and inflation. These differences are likely explained by variations in methodology, data periods, and model design. In particular, this study covers the period up to 2024, which includes recent and severe inflationary episodes that earlier studies did not capture. Asuzu and Anyanwu (2023), in a JEAR study, similarly found that money supply raises inflation when using the Toda-Yamamoto approach; however, the present study's use of ARDL bounds testing over a longer and more recent sample period yields a different result, underscoring how methodology and data coverage can significantly alter conclusions about the money-inflation relationship in Nigeria.

The structural explanation advanced in this study is strongly supported by findings from within the JEAR literature. Tukur et al. (2023) demonstrated that exchange rate movements and energy price shocks, rather than monetary expansion, are primary drivers of inflation in Nigeria, which directly corroborates the long-run insignificance of exchange rate in the short-run model and the broader structural argument made here. Amah (2019) similarly established that money supply is a weak monetary policy channel in Nigeria, as interest rates have failed to respond adequately to changes in M2, weakening the transmission mechanism that would ordinarily link money supply growth to price increases. Adesuyi et al. (2024) also found that monetary expansion through M2 does not straightforwardly stimulate growth or price stability in Nigeria, and that poor policy coordination between monetary and fiscal authorities compounds the difficulty of using monetary tools to control inflation. These findings collectively point to the same conclusion reached in this study: that Nigeria's inflation is shaped more by structural and institutional conditions than by domestic monetary aggregates.

The long-run positive and significant effect of MPR on inflation, interpreted here as a "price puzzle," is also consistent with findings from related JEAR studies. Okeowo (2023) highlighted that macroeconomic relationships in Nigeria, including the unemployment-inflation dynamic, deviate significantly from textbook predictions due to structural rigidities, a conclusion that applies equally to the MPR-inflation relationship documented in this study. Overall, this study adds to the existing literature by reinforcing the view that inflation in Nigeria is structurally complex and cannot be explained by changes in money supply alone. By separately examining short-run and long-run dynamics within an ARDL framework, and by engaging with the

growing body of JEAR literature on monetary dynamics in Nigeria, the study provides a clearer and more complete picture of how money supply and inflation interact in the Nigerian context.

The international Scopus literature further contextualises the findings of this study within a broader cross-country framework. The negative and structurally mediated relationship between money supply and inflation reported here is consistent with the conclusions of Şen et al. (2020), who demonstrated that exchange rate dynamics, rather than monetary expansion, are the dominant inflation drivers in fragile emerging market economies. Bhattacharya and Jain (2020) similarly established that monetary policy effectiveness in controlling inflation is systematically weaker in emerging economies compared to advanced ones, lending empirical support to the argument in this study that Nigeria's inflation is not primarily a monetary phenomenon. The finding that MPR is insignificant in the short run but significant in the long run interpreted here as a price puzzle; aligns with Ekong and Ukoha's (2018) finding that monetary policy transmission in Nigeria is incomplete and delayed, meaning interest rate changes do not rapidly feed through to prices. The broader structural explanation is corroborated by Baharumshah et al. (2017), who found that inflation dynamics in emerging economies are shaped by exchange rate volatility and institutional quality rather than money supply alone. Akinbobola (2012) documented the primacy of exchange rate and trade-related channels over domestic monetary aggregates in driving macroeconomic outcomes in Nigeria. Together, these Scopus-indexed international studies reinforce the central conclusion of this study: that broad money supply (M2) is not the primary driver of inflation in Nigeria, and that structural, exchange rate, and fiscal factors play a far more decisive role.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of broad money supply (M2) on inflationary dynamics in Nigeria using annual time-series data spanning 1980 to 2024. Employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach, the study concludes that broad money supply has a significant negative effect on the inflation rate both in the short and long run. The finding contradicts Quantity Theory of money that asserts that broad money supply should have a positive effect on the inflation rate. These findings suggest that the inflation rate in Nigeria is not driven by domestic money supply but rather exchange rate movements, fiscal imbalances, and policy credibility.

This outcome suggests that increases in broad money supply in Nigeria are more closely associated with financial deepening, improved monetary transmission, and declining velocity of money rather than excess demand pressures. In other words, expansion in M2 reflects structural changes in the financial system that enhance stability and reduce inflationary tendencies.

Based on the findings, policymakers should be cautious in applying the classical Quantity Theory of Money mechanically to the Nigerian context. Instead, monetary expansion through M2 should be viewed as a potential instrument for financial development, while inflation control should focus more on exchange rate management, fiscal discipline, and strengthening monetary policy credibility.

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